

SIKKIM; A ROLE MODEL OF ECOTOURISM IN INDIA: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract:-Sikkim has been named as the best region to visit in 2014 by a leading global travel guide, Lonely Planet. It is the largest travel guide book publisher in the world. Lonely planet caters the travel fraternity worldwide and its recommendations are received by heart by numerous travel enthusiasts, seasonal backpackers and vacationers. Lonely Planet describes Sikkim as “It's clean (plastic bags are banned) and the mountain air is fresh. Best of all the people are among India's most friendly, with a charming manner that's unobtrusive and slightly shy”. This recommendation could be the big boost for Sikkim and its ecotourism policy. This research paper aims to critically analyze the eco-tourism policy of Sikkim, which endeavors to create a responsible and sustainable tourism, the reasons behind Lonely Planet recommendation and the impact of eco-tourism policy on biodiversity and well being of local population.

Keywords: Lonely Planet best in travel 2014, Sikkim, Gangtok, Namchi, Tibetan Buddhism, Eco-tourism in India, Sustainable development, Responsible tourism.

OBJECTIVE

India has some of the world's most biodiverse regions. It hosts 3 biodiversity hotspots: the Western Ghats, the Himalayas and the Indo-Burma region. These hotspots have numerous endemic species. The State of Sikkim is located in the area of the Biodiversity Hotspot of Eastern Himalaya Region. Biodiversity hotspots are defined as areas featuring exceptional concentrations of endemic species and experiencing exceptional loss of habitat. Species are described as endemic if they are unique to a specific area or region, and don't naturally occur anywhere else. Due to their limited ranges, endemic species are particularly vulnerable to extinction. To promote conservation incentive and suitable livelihood option for the natives, the Government of Sikkim has formulated an Ecotourism policy based on two primary motives; “poverty alleviation” and “nature conservation”.

The result of these actions are established in due time and Sikkim now has the reputation of cleanest state due to conservation measures, crime free region due to growing economic activity and earned the recognition of best region to visit in 2014 by a leading global travel guide, Lonely Planet.

This paper aims to systematically analyze:

The eco-tourism policy of Sikkim

The reasons, why it was chosen as a best region to visit in 2014, by Lonely Planet.

The impact of eco-tourism policy on biodiversity and well being of local population.

RESEARCH DESIGN

1.Secondary Data

Extensive review of literature was done to collect information and get a fair understanding of the kind of research previously conducted on similar issues in order to understand the term ecotourism and its possible impact on the ecology as well community. For this, many libraries in the national capital region (Delhi-NCR) has been consulted and also national and international journals were reviewed which provided the exact feel of research problem.

Content of the published material and opinion given by various eminent scholars, environmentalist and researchers have been observed and analyzed in order to understand the different aspects of the problem and its preclusion. Qualitative content analysis was conducted as per the need of the study.

To make deep understanding about the ecotourism effort in different parts of the world, a qualitative case study approach has been chosen to provide an idea about the successful implementation efforts that changed the relationship between development and conservation for the betterment of local community and at the same time preserving the precious ecosystems. Qualitative case study methodology provides tools for researchers to study complex phenomena within their contexts.

The sources of secondary data that were examined are also taken from:

Official websites, promotional materials and information provided by the tourism department and other related departments of the Sikkim.

Lonely planet website.

2.Primary Data

A focus group has been formed to add the audience perspective into the study. A focus group is a form of qualitative research in which a group of people are asked about their perceptions, opinions, beliefs, and attitudes towards a product, service, concept, advertisement, idea, or packaging. Questions were asked in an interactive group setting where participants were free to talk with other group members. A group of 20 people were selected on the basis of their knowledge and interest about the ecotourism. These people include researchers, academician, and industry experts within the age group of 30 to 50.

INTRODUCTION

Eco-Tourism

The World Conservation Union (IUCN) defines ecotourism as: “environmentally responsible travel and visitation to relatively undisturbed natural areas, in order to enjoy and appreciate nature (and any accompanying cultural features - both past and present) that promotes conservation, has low negative visitor impact, and provides for beneficially active socio-economic involvement of local populations” (IUCN, 1996).

According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO) “tourism that involves travelling to relatively undisturbed natural areas with the specified objective of studying, admiring and enjoying the scenery and its wild plants and animals, as well as any existing cultural aspects [both of the past and the present] found in these areas is defined as ecotourism”. An optimum number of environment friendly visitor activities, which do not have any serious impact on the ecosystem and the local community and the positive involvement of the local community in maintaining the ecological balance are some of its key elements (UNWTO, 2002).

The International Ecotourism Society defines ecotourism as: “responsible travel to natural areas that conserves the environment and improves the welfare of local people”.

Ecotourism is considered as a powerful alternative to the traditional form of mass tourism. Its important characteristics are:

- It takes place in natural setting
- It is sustainable in nature
- It increases awareness towards conservation of natural and cultural assets
- It is carried out in small scale as per the carrying capacity of the host
- It provides economic benefits and employment opportunities for locals

It is one of the proud moments and a matter of immense joy for tourism industry in Sikkim, to top in the chart of best region to visit in 2014 by Lonely Planet which is a leading travel publication in world and is equally popular among first time vacationers to frequent backpackers.

Sikkim: A mystical land

Sikkim is truly a mystical land, a confluence of advancement and mysticism. It is India's least populated state, hosts Kanchenjunga, the world's third-highest peak, have borders with Tibet, Bhutan and Nepal and only open border with China (Nathula-Pass). Very little is known about its history as it was added to the Indian Republic only in 1975.

Sikkim is the first Indian state to frame an eco-tourism policy with the help of Japanese and American experts. It started developing tourist destinations & circuits and popularizing less developed areas, without creating much load on the sensitive ecology of Himalaya by creating local infrastructure and a lot of activities to attract tourists. Sikkim modified central

projects like the “Indira Awas Yojana” to develop village and eco-tourism. Funds were made available to build extra space and sanitation facility for western tourists. This is precisely what Lonely Planet has recognized: the sustainable community-based tourism model that Sikkim has successfully developed in less-developed areas of the state. Adventure tourism is also being promoted that includes trekking, white water rafting, rock climbing and skiing. As lonely planet mentioned about Sikkim “finding the 'real' Sikkim is just a matter of hiking away from the metalled roads”.

In pre-historic times Sikkim was inhabited by three tribes namely Naong, Chang and the Mon. The Lepcha who entered Sikkim sometimes later absorbed them completely. The origin of Lepchas is shrouded in mystery. It is believed that, they came from somewhere on the borders of Tibet and Burma. The Lepchas were a very peace loving people, shy, deeply religious and worshipped nature, which can still be sensed among the natives of Sikkim. It is a largely crime-free state and its people are hospitable and warm. The majority of its citizens are Nepalese, and the main religions are Hinduism and Vajrayana Buddhism.

Sikkim has 227 lakes, 28 mountain peaks, more than 80 glaciers & 100 rivers and hot springs with temperature up to 122 degrees F. Sikkim's climate ranges from tropical, temperate to alpine. It also receives regular rainfall.

Eco-Tourism in Sikkim

Sikkim is a natural hot spot of biodiversity; and the number of species of flora per unit area in this region is extremely high. Sikkim constitutes only 0.2% of the entire geographic region of India but it is the habitat for nearly one-fourth of all plant species found in the country. Due to its difficult terrain and poverty in the state the focus has been placed on developing ecotourism that utilizes the state's abundant natural environment and unique culture. Also to negate the impact on the natural environment due to rapid growth in tourists the State government of Sikkim has taken many initiatives to create the synergy between nature and development activities by giving the benefits of tourism to the villages. This has resulted in the setting up of many village home stays in different parts of the state.

The Department of Forests, Environment and Wildlife Management (DFEWM) is implementing Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA) assisted Sikkim Biodiversity Conservation and Forest Management Project. The project is for a period of ten years commencing from 2010-2011 to 2019-2020 at a total cost of Rs.330.57 Crores. The Project objective is to strengthen biodiversity conservation activities and forest management capacity, and to improve livelihood for the local people who are dependent on forests by promoting sustainable biodiversity conservation, a forestation and income generation activities including eco-tourism for the community development, thereby contributing environment conservation and harmonized socio-economic development of Sikkim.

Sikkim Himalayan home stay program promotes ecotourism in rural areas of Sikkim. It is supported by UNESCO Paris, Norwegian Govt. & the Principality of Andorra & implemented by Ecotourism & Conservation Society of Sikkim (ECOSS), which is a nongovernmental organization. The Sikkim Himalayan Homestays Program is operational at Dzongu (North Sikkim), Pastanga (East Sikkim), Yuksom (West Sikkim) and Kewzing (South Sikkim). ECOSS is also developing new rural ecotourism sites at Naitam (East Sikkim), Lingee Payong (South Sikkim) and Ray Mindu (East Sikkim).

This community based tourism creates a memorable experience for the visitor who gets a chance to interact with local inhabitants and participate in their daily lives. It also helps local communities protect their cultural and natural heritage for future generations.

According to the statistics of tourist arrival in the state of Sikkim, by Tourism Department, till the month of April 2013, about 69054 domestic and 4895 International tourists have paid their visit in comparison to 65341 domestic tourists and 3939 International tourists during the same period last year. With a view to promote tourism in Sikkim, restrictions on the entry for foreigners into restricted areas of Sikkim have been relaxed. Foreigners can now visit Gangtok, Rumtek, Phodong, Pemayangtse and the Yuksom -Zongri trekking route on the basis of restricted area permits for a period of fifteen days.

Highlights of Sikkim's Ecotourism Policy

Sikkim's ecotourism policy is in perfect tune with the conservation measures. It states that; there would be little construction based on the absolute requirement, no felling of a single tree, and rigorous plantation would be the key to any specific or jointly managed ecotourism program. Also the impact assessment for each location and area would be done annually for corrective and improvement measures.

“Sikkim - the Ultimate Tourist Destination” is the policy motto of the state. The state is employing a system of environmental fees, and permits for entries, and stay time restrictions in some environmentally sensitive high altitude/pristine areas.

Operationalization of tourism in various modes, such as village tourism, nature tourism, wildlife tourism, trekking/adventure tourism, and cultural tourism in the state and institutionalization of tourism management at the community level may be useful.

Promotion and use of local art & craft, cuisines, etc., along with organizing tourism fairs and festivals.

Imparting training in tourism related service industries.

Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC Council)

The “Global Sustainable Tourism Council” is a multi-stakeholder global tourism organization under the umbrella of the UN, and aims to bring all stakeholders together to achieve sustainable tourism. GSTC was established as a membership council; to serve as the international body for promoting the increased knowledge, understanding and adoption of sustainable tourism practices based on the GSTC criteria, which are a set of global guiding principles.

Sikkim Ecotourism Policy based on GSTC Criteria

The silent features of Sikkim Ecotourism Policy are:

To bring businesses, governments, non-governmental organizations, academia, individuals and communities together on a common platform of understanding of ecotourism and offering learning experience for their collaboration for nature conservation efforts.

To promote ecotourism in a sustainable manner based on the GSTC criteria

To empower local communities with the emphasis on economically weaker section to manage ecotourism to conserve biodiversity, culture and tradition.

To reduce the negative impacts of tourism the tourist activities are regulated through a policy.

Sikkim Ecotourism Council (SEC)

To organize and ensure an effective management and implementation of ecotourism objectives and principles, the Sikkim Ecotourism Council (SEC) is proposed as an autonomous council that will have an executing arm which is the Ecotourism Directorate (ED) working under the Forest, Environment and Wildlife Management Department (FEWMD). The Council is proposed to have a local village level operational system which incorporates various Community-Based Organizations (CBO) working in tandem with Panchayat, Non Governmental Organisation, Tourism Development Committee (TDC), Self-help Groups (SHG) and other local people's representative groups. The supreme patron of the SEC would be the chief minister of the state of the Sikkim. The Sikkim Ecotourism Council is proposed to deal with;

1. Bringing all stakeholders on a common platform, establish guidelines for ecotourism, and revise them from time to time as per the requirements and guidelines that are consistent with the Code of Conduct for responsible tourism prepared by the Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India and adopted by Dept of Tourism and Civil Aviation (Govt. of Sikkim)
2. Monitoring and evaluating ecotourism activities to ensure minimum negative impacts on the biodiversity and ecosystems of Sikkim
3. Establishing Sikkim ecotourism safety standards and emergency procedures and facilitate the implementation of those with relevant organizations in case of need.

Sikkim: Top region to visit in 2014 by Lonely Planet

Sikkim has been named as the best region to visit in 2014 by Lonely Planet, a leading global travel guide. Previously it has also bagged the “Most Innovative and Unique Tourism Project Award” 2010-11, for the vision and construction of world class pilgrimage cum cultural tourism complex (Siddesvara Dham) at Solophok, Namchi in south Sikkim. It had also bagged the Best state in Campaign Clean India 2010-11 award for the State Government's initiatives in maintaining a clean and green Sikkim, efficient garbage management and disposal, health and hygiene, green mission and maintaining the environment and biodiversity of the state.

According to the guide, "Picking up national accolades in 2012 for being India's cleanest state with the most innovative tourism project, Sikkim has set new benchmarks for responsible travel in the country". It further says “Checkbox sightseeing has rapidly made way for sustainable community-based tourism in less developed areas, while eco-friendly policies have lent new vigor to the virginal Himalayan wilderness that drapes the region's mountains". Praising the food in the region, the guide notes that organic farming is the new mantra in Sikkim and is being promoted in a big way. With a new airport scheduled to open near Gangtok, the guide says in 2014 several hours of transit time will be cut and one could fly in directly from major Indian metros.

Community Participation in Ecotourism

Ministry of Environment & Forests, Government of India, has released a report called; “Governance for Sustaining Himalayan Ecosystem (G-SHE): Guidelines and Best Practices” that sheds light on the impacts of tourism on mountain ecosystems and biological resources. It states that community based ecotourism emerges as one of the sustainable alternatives to the presently practised commercial tourism in already over saturated hill towns like Nainital, Mussoorie, Shimla, Kullu-Manali, Gangtok, etc. In spite of efforts by some state governments (e.g., Sikkim), the pace at which tourism is growing every year is rapid (from nearly 15,000 tourists in 1980 to 3,50,000 tourists in 2007 in Sikkim). Yet, the efforts that have been made by Sikkim can serve as a basis of responsible tourism in other Himalayan states.

With Support from United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Global Environment Facility (GEF), the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India and National Biodiversity Authority (NBA) are currently implementing the first national project on “Strengthening the Implementation of the Biological Diversity Act & Rules with Focus on its Access and Benefit Sharing Provisions”, at the total cost of US\$ 9,839,000 in five states viz., Andhra Pradesh, Gujarat, Himachal Pradesh, Sikkim and West Bengal. The duration of the project is 3 years (April 2011-March 2014). The sharing of benefits concept would enable communities to participate and remain connected with conservation program for better coordination of activities besides ensuring all stakeholders to be involved in the project and contribute to the conservation and sustainability.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSIONS

The state of Sikkim is setting new milestones in achieving miracles due to its conservation policies. Sikkim is greenest state in the country. Sikkim has become the only state to have increased its forest cover in the past two decades and has launched a Rs 31 crore project of plantation in additional 1,000 hectares during 12th Five Year Plan to further enhance its green area. The forest cover in the state has been increased to 47.34 per cent in 2013 from 43.95 per cent in 1993 as compared to 21 per cent of the national average.

To develop Sikkim into a model Green State, the Government of Sikkim has launched its 8th phase of State Green Mission on June, 2013 and declared June 15- 30 as Paryavaran Mahotsav in Sikkim, every year. The State Green Mission is a people oriented program that seeks to benefit the masses with the view to raising avenue plantation and beautification of all vacant and waste lands to further reinforce wide spread recognition of Sikkim being a Green State. The coverage of this program includes the road reserves along the National Highway, State High way, District Roads and Other roads. It is also proposed to take up plantation in the Government and Private vacant lands, along Water falls and streams, Religious Institutions, other Government Institution lands.

To further enhance the tourist activity the Khangchendzonga National Park, that includes Mt Khanchendzonga (8,586 m) – the third highest mountain in the world, has been nominated for the recognition as UNESCO World Heritage List, which comprises more than a quarter of the land area of the State and has significant cultural and religious values.

Eco-tourism plays a very significant role in reducing the dependence of local communities (both forest dwelling and forest dependent) on the forests. Eco-tourism provides them with a means of employment and also makes them stakeholders in the overall development process. The eco-tourists also constitute a ready made market for Non-Timber Forest Products (NTFPs) such as honey and local items like embroidery products, handicrafts, etc. at their very doorstep. Eco-tourism could also be used as an effective communication and extension tool to convince the local communities and especially the children, about the benefits of conserving forests and natural ecosystems.

The state of Sikkim has recognized all these opportunities and implemented them effectively for the betterment of their own people and becoming a role model for the rest of the country.

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